

From ‘model minority’ to ‘outsiders’: COVID-19 and the surge of anti-Chinese sentiment

Luiz Valério P. Trindade¹
Claudia Rosa Acevedo²

¹PhD in Sociology from the University of Southampton (UK)

Affiliate to IPIE (International Panel on the Information Environment, Switzerland)

²PhD in Economics from USP – Universidade de São Paulo (Brazil)

Assistant Professor of Marketing (EACH-USP – Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil)

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents a critical analysis of the interplay between the emergence of COVID-19 and the recent surge in anti-Chinese sentiment observed in Western societies. To achieve this, it reviews the concept of stigma and the ‘model minority’ stereotype, discusses the development of contemporary anti-Chinese sentiment and, finally, analyses the role played by major social media platforms in this phenomenon. In so doing, three intertwined arguments are presented. First, rather than being a completely new phenomenon, anti-Chinese sentiment has been dormant for a long time, probably shielded by the ‘model minority’ stereotype, and has now resurfaced with the emergence of COVID-19. Second, although some voices refer to this phenomenon as racism and others as xenophobic manifestations, a critical discourse analysis of a sample of publicly available Twitter posts demonstrates that, in reality, racism and xenophobia both permeate anti-Chinese sentiment. Finally, major social media platforms represent a powerful vehicle enabling the wide and instantaneous dissemination of discourses that construct Chinese people according to three main categories: a) strange people, b) the perfect scapegoat, and c) the undesirable citizen.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19; anti-Chinese sentiment; racism; xenophobia, social media; critical discourse analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

From early January 2020, news began to circulate regarding a new respiratory disease caused by a virus and that the first city to be strongly affected was Wuhan in China. In a matter of four to eight weeks, the virus had reached other Asian countries, Europe and, later on, the Americas (Taylor, 2020). In addition to the enormous challenges this pandemic

has brought to the global health system, there are important and correlated societal impacts that also demand critical reflection. Within this scenario, a considerable surge in Sinophobia has been observed in numerous countries, often fuelled by factors such as fake news or disinformation, panic, ingrained racism, and extremist political discourses (Rafi, 2020). Against this background, this paper explores the shift in perceptions regarding Asian people in Western societies from intelligent, hard-working and tech-savvy to ‘outsiders’ or undesirable people.

First, however, it is important to emphasise that Sinophobia, “which is understood as the intersection of fear and hatred of China” (Billé, 2015, p. 10), is not a new social phenomenon. In fact, Sinophobic manifestations have been present since the second half of the eighteenth century when China was portrayed as “the prototype of a stagnant and despotic society” (Zhang, 2008, p. 98). Moreover, two emblematic works by Rupert (1911) and Stoddard (1921) that conveyed Sinophobic ideas contended that Oriental peoples such as Chinese, Japanese, and Russians represented a menace to the white Western civilization. According to these authors, Western civilization was at risk of being subjugated by these Oriental ‘invaders’. In the current scenario, evidence suggests that not only the pandemic has contributed to the resurgence of this ancient anti-Chinese sentiment in several Western societies, but also that the discourses are highly aggressive and, in certain circumstances, have led to violent attacks against Chinese and/or Asian people perceived as such (BBC, 2020a; Stampa, 2020).

Furthermore, social media has provided a platform for this surge in anti-Chinese sentiment as a large number of people have been conveying their aggressive messages through this virtual environment (Rafi, 2020; Schild *et al.*, 2020). Thus, the emergence of this digital technology has enabled

offenders to spread hate speech at a pace and in proportions not previously seen in history. Furthermore, similar patterns have been observed in relation to other phenomena such as the construction and dissemination of racist discourses against black people, islamophobia, misogyny, and a myriad of bigoted attitudes (e.g., Awan, 2016; Jane, 2017; Trindade, 2019). Moreover, it also calls our attention to the fact that the emergence of this phenomenon contrasts with previous portrayals of Asian people as permeated by positive attributes which characterised them as 'role models' or the so-called 'model minority' stereotype.

Therefore, to investigate the surge in anti-Chinese sentiment, it has been reviewed existing

II. STIGMATISATION AND THE 'MODEL MINORITY' STEREOTYPE

The origin of the word stigma can be traced back to ancient Greece where runaway slaves used to have their bodies branded with the letter 'F' once they had been captured to highlight their status as fugitives (Goffman, 1963; Weiner and Perry, 1988). Similarly, in colonial Brazil, African slaves also used to have their bodies branded to evidence their enslavement to wider society and, consequently, their socially inferior position (Conrad, 1983).

Over time, this definition has evolved "to embrace any mark or sign for perceived or inferred conditions of deviations from a prototype or norm" (Weiner and Perry, 1988, p. 738). Today, stigma comprises a series of negative attributes that consistently undermine a person's value and reduce their relevance as a member of a given social group (Goffman, 1963). It can also represent social constructions fuelled by pre-conceived depreciative perceptions regarding other people and therefore are not necessarily supported by concrete evidence. In fact, undesirable characteristics are at the core of stigmatisation processes because, in relation to the dominant or hegemonic group, stigmas represent "negative outcomes or unwanted effects" (Weiner and Perry, 1988, p. 738).

Thus, it becomes clear that, in effect, stigmatisation encompasses an asymmetric power relation as those who inflict stigmatisation upon others enjoy a condition which, in certain social configurations, bestows on them the appropriate means to engage in this practice (Major and O'Brien, 2005). Furthermore, "stigmatisation occurs when a person possesses (or is believed to possess) some attributes or characteristics that conveys a social identity that is devalued in a particular social context" (Major and O'Brien, 2005, p. 394). Thus, in the eyes

literature addressing the concepts of stigmatisation (Goffman, 1963; Weiner and Perry, 1988; Major and O'Brien, 2005) and the 'model minority' stereotype (Delener and Neelankavil, 1990; Cohen, 1992; Taylor and Stern, 1997; Kawai, 2005; Taylor *et al.*, 2005). Subsequently, it is discussed the development of contemporary anti-Chinese sentiment and the conduction of a critical discourse analysis of a selection of publicly available Twitter posts. Finally, the conclusion weaves together the distinct aspects raised in the paper and elucidates important considerations regarding the phenomenon under investigation.

of those who inflict stigmatisation upon others, certain people or social groups possess a set of innate or specific attributes that 'mark' them as different from hegemonic social groups and cause them to be devalued. As a consequence, "stigma directly affects the stigmatised via mechanisms of discrimination, expectancy confirmation, and automatic stereotype activation, and indirectly via threats to personal and social identity" (Major and O'Brien, 2005, p. 393).

Conversely, although stigmatisation is essentially negative and depreciative in nature, the 'model minority' stereotype conveys a set of positive attributes regarding certain social groups (usually Asian people). This stereotype implies a series of differentiated attributes that add values which position the social group as 'role models'. Developed by Delener and Neelankavil (1990) and Cohen (1992) in studies exploring the response of white Americans to advertisements involving Asian American models, it establishes that, unlike Afro Americans and Hispanics, Asian Americans are often portrayed as possessing specific positive attributes (e.g., hardworking, intelligent, tech savvy, ethical, business-oriented, and so forth). Moreover, this stereotype was developed based on the generalisation of demographic data revealing that, in comparison to white Americans, on average Asian Americans enjoyed a higher income level, better schooling, and higher social capital (Delener and Neelankavil, 1990; Cohen, 1992; Taylor and Stern, 1997; Taylor *et al.*, 2005). Although the concept was developed in the US, it had already been explored in different social contexts such as Brazil (Santos and Acevedo, 2013), Canada (Pon, 2000; Ho, 2014) and in the UK (Yeh, 2014), enhancing our understanding of the cross-

cultural aspects of the 'positive' stereotyping of Asian people.

Nevertheless, like stigmatisation, it has been the subject of criticism due to its negative nature. For instance, both Taylor and Stern (1997) and Santos and Acevedo (2013) contend that exaggerated positive stereotypes can cause emotional distress and conflictive social relations as not all Asian individuals fit this 'model'. Taylor *et al.* (2005) also assert that one of the major flaws in the 'model minority' stereotype is that it disregards differences in social and cultural backgrounds among countries such as China, Japan and Korea, and places them altogether in a single and uniform 'Asian box'. Kawai (2005) argues that rather than being positive, the model minority stereotype in fact represents a pernicious stigmatisation of Asian Americans. In addition, Kraus and Eun (2020) claim that this stereotype simplifies and distorts the life experiences of Asian Americans.

Nevertheless despite its numerous flaws, the 'model minority' stereotype might well have contributed to the integration of Asian people in most Western societies because, in contrast to their predominantly negative portrayal in the early twentieth century (Rupert, 1911; Stoddard, 1921), the positive attributes assigned to them do not represent a threat to the established hegemonic social structure. However, during the emergence of COVID-19, with China as its initial epicentre, seems to have shattered the 'model minority' stereotype assigned to Asian people not only in the US but also in several other social contexts, as evidenced in numerous news articles (e.g., Cebron and Petit, 2020; Lee, 2020; Trilling, 2020). Within this context, a profound shift in peoples' perceptions of Asian individuals appears to have occurred. Rather than 'role models', they have become 'outsiders', even if they are native citizens in the countries where they have been insulted and stigmatised.

III. CONTEMPORARY ANTI-CHINESE SENTIMENT

As stated previously, the emergence of COVID-19 has led to numerous accounts of physical and verbal attacks against Asian people in countries such as France (Cebron and Petit, 2020), Germany (Hemkentokrax, 2020), Italy (Stampa, 2020), Spain (Maldita, 2020), and the US (Rich, 2020). There have also been voices claiming that the mainstream media has played a distinctive role in disseminating distorted perceptions that, ultimately, might have triggered anti-Chinese sentiment. For instance, Rafi (2020, p. 2) argues that "the world, in many ways, was built on the conversation of fear through millions of articles published in large-circulation newspapers". Continuing his reflection, Rafi contends that newspapers "created the discourse of fear that raised anti-China and anti-Chinese sentiments" (Rafi, 2020, p. 4).

However, whilst it is indeed relevant to critically analyse the role played by mainstream media in triggering or influencing the surge of anti-Chinese sentiment, it is important to remember that behind each news article and headline there are people with their own biases, perceptions, and positionality. In fact, Kolko *et al.* (2000, p. 5) already called our attention to the fact that "race matters in cyberspace precisely because all of us who spend time online are already shaped by the ways in which race matter offline, and we cannot help bring our own knowledge, experiences, and values with us when we log on". Thus, in addition to the business agenda and strategic interests of news corporations, the individuals who write journalistic stories are also

influenced by their own set of values, beliefs, and ideologies, which in turn can influence the construction of their journalistic narratives.

In line with this reflection, the present study argues that what has been witnessed was not the construction of anti-Chinese sentiment *per se* but rather its resurgence, which implies that it has most probably been dormant for a long time and that the emergence of COVID-19 has enabled it to resurface. Likewise, as discussed in the previous section, the 'model minority' stereotype might have helped to shield Asian people from stigmatisation in Western societies owing to its associated 'positive' attributes. However, once this 'shield' was removed or put aside because of COVID-19, this social group became exposed and, consequently, subjected to stigmatisation.

In an analysis of discourses of fear fostered by mainstream media, Rafi (2020) discusses several notable examples worthy of further reflection. For instance, the Wall Street Journal has stated, 'China is the real sick man of Asia', while the British newspapers *Daily Mail* and *The Sun*, "ascribed the virus with Chinese eating bats, snakes, and dogs" (Rafi, 2020, p. 4). A historical perspective on these discourses suggests that in fact they embed a series of ancient depreciative perceptions regarding Asian societies. In the eighteenth century, for example, Eurocentric thinking depicted China as a backward and 'despotic' society (Zhang, 2008). Indeed, while for many years, ideas of modernity and intellectual superiority were associated with European societies,

Asia was perceived as ‘the other’, backward and stuck in the past (Billé, 2015). Moreover, in the early twentieth century in the US, newspapers and magazines used to display depreciative cartoons depicting Irish, Italian, and Chinese immigrants as undesirable people. In the case of Chinese immigrants in particular, these publications portrayed them as parasitic locusts devouring what Americans hold dear (Chandra, 2020).

Furthermore, it is also relevant to highlight that in the early twentieth century Rupert (1911) portrayed Asian people as the ‘Yellow Peril’ or a menace to the Western civilization and, likewise, Stoddard (1921) viewed Chinese and Japanese people as eminent threats to Western white supremacy. Finally, in a recent study investigating anti-Chinese sentiment in Latin America, Armony and Velásquez (2015, p. 338) revealed that during the

IV. THE AMPLIFYING POWER OF SOCIAL MEDIA

As stated in the Introduction, a prominent arena in which contemporary anti-Chinese sentiment (or, more broadly, anti-Asian people) has been manifested is on major social media platforms (Rafi, 2020; Schild *et al.*, 2020). A possible explanatory clue to this phenomenon was identified in a study conducted by Walsh (2020) regarding the role digital technologies play in fostering collective panic. In this study, the author classifies social media in three major categories: a) as an object of anxiety, b) a facilitator of division, and c) as instruments of panic production. Walsh thus argues that social media constitute a powerful vehicle that enables users to become active agents in constructing and disseminating a myriad of hate speech which can potentially trigger collective panic. In line with this reflection, Klein (2018) contends that bigotry in the online environment can potentially lead to violent actions in the offline world. He argues that most of the time, the hateful and/or hysterical narratives fostered on social media are fuelled by unfounded allegations and pre-conceived assumptions about the nature of ‘the other’.

A similar pattern can be observed in other forms of online hate speech such as racism, islamophobia, and misogyny (e.g. Awan, 2016; Jane, 2017; Trindade, 2019). These studies revealed a set of important characteristics regarding the enactment of hate speech on social media. First, contrary to what most users might believe, the online and offline environments are not detached but closely

early nineteenth century in Mexico, newspapers used to depict the arriving Chinese immigrant workforce as “living in unhealthy conditions with ‘uncivilized’ eating habits” in their homeland.

To a certain extent, these ideas and negative portrayals of Asian peoples also coalesce with the concept of Orientalism developed by Said (2003), which refers to Western societies’ pre-conceived assumptions of Oriental societies as predominantly violent, backward, sensual, exotic, and numerous other reductionist stereotypes. Such depictions serve to legitimise the normality and hegemony of Eurocentric ideals. Consequently, although anti-Chinese ideas, portrayals, and perceptions have not been openly verbalised for a long time, it does not mean that they have vanished. Instead, they might have simply remained dormant for a long period of time.

intertwined, which means that discriminatory, hateful, and xenophobic discourses disseminated on social media can have an impact on people’s lives beyond the virtual environment. Furthermore, the powerful networking characteristics of social media platforms enable users to instantly convey their xenophobic messages and ideologies to a wide audience, attracting masses of like-minded users and amplifying the reach and reverberation of their voices. Finally, the increasing spread of discriminatory and xenophobic discourses on social media can potentially lead to its naturalisation as an indissociable component of the online landscape.

V. ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL MEDIA POSTS

Twitter was chosen as the source of data for this study as it is a social media platform that has become increasingly popular across the world as a public arena in which people can express their opinions, sentiments, and points of view on a wide variety of subjects (Pak and Paroubek, 2010; Zhao, 2013; Younis, 2015). Evidence also indicates that as Twitter’s popularity and penetration increase exponentially worldwide, there is a corresponding surge in the construction and dissemination of hate speech across this platform, which makes it a highly appropriate source of research data (Jane, 2017; Evolvi, 2018).

Adopting an approach similar to that employed in previous studies exploring Twitter (e.g., Pak and Paroubek, 2010; Zhao, 2013; Younis, 2015; Evolvi, 2018), data were gathered using text mining

on search engines in April 2023 using a series of keywords (e.g., dirty Chinese, infected Chinese, strange Chinese eating habits, Chinese go away, Chinese virus, Chinese scum, disgusting Chinese, backward Chinese, amongst other similar variations). This facilitated the identification of twenty relevant Tweets, from which twelve were analysed. Regarding this small sample size, Silver and Lewins (2014, p. 25) argue that “often, relatively small amounts of data and/or number of texts are utilised when conducting a discourse analysis, as they are analysed at a very fine level of detail”.

In addition, it is also pertinent to explain that the use of social media platforms as a resource has the advantage of providing social science researchers with rich data spontaneously generated by users. However, regardless of the easy access to such data, ethical considerations regarding users’ privacy must guide the methodological procedure (Zimmer, 2010). In fact, a review of previous studies exploring social media platforms as study objects revealed that the adoption of initiatives to safeguard users’ privacy is a common concern (Trindade, 2019). Thus, the approach adopted in the present study was to work solely with publicly available social media posts. Furthermore, the study avoided the disclosure of personal information (e.g., users’ real names, users’ aliases, hyperlinks, images, geographical localisation, etc.) that could identify actual research participants, unless they were public figures such as political leaders.

Consistent with previous qualitative studies exploring social media platforms (e.g. Khosravini and Sarkhoh, 2017; Torkington and Ribeiro, 2019; Trindade, 2019), this study adopted the methodology of critical discourse analysis. This was appropriate and relevant for this study because it unveils the embedded ideologies, social representations, and power relation dynamics expressed through discourse. Moreover, “discourse is not only a tool for representing social practices, [it] also constitutes practices such as power, sovereignty, prejudice and resistance” (Yerlikaya, 2019, p. 195).

Having said that, the data were analysed using an iterative process akin to that employed in grounded theory in that it allowed the data to reveal the predominant thematic categories, rather than starting from a pre-defined set (Starks and Trinidad, 2007). This led to the emergence of three major themes: a) *aspects of strangeness in Chinese people*, b) *the quest for a scapegoat* and c) *the undesirable citizen*. These are discussed in detail in the following sections.

VI. ASPECTS OF STRANGENESS IN CHINESE PEOPLE

One of the main characteristics in the stigmatisation of social groups is the establishment of differentiation between the in-group (i.e., the dominant and hegemonic group in a given social context) and ‘the others’ who are considered the out-group (Weiner and Perry, 1988). One of the ways to achieve this is by highlighting deviant attributes of the out-group in such a way as to reinforce the hegemonic condition of the in-group. In fact, “a stigmatised group is an out-group relative to the dominant group in a culture or society, and the stigmatised groups are devalued not only by specific in-groups but by the broader society or culture” (Weiner and Perry, 1988, p. 609). In line with this reflection, the following sample of Twitter posts depict this ideological construction occurring.

Tweet #01: I am trying to keep an open mind like “it is ok that these cultures like to eat strange things”. Meanwhile, I am thinking... “filthy godless people spreading disgusting diseases via their lust for foul foods... no wonder it took them 1,000 years to (almost) join the modern world”. (Posted on: 26/01/2020 - 32 comments; 7 retweets; 66 likes)

Tweet #02: How does such a backward population live in the same country that produces state-of-the-art computer technology? In addition to their population involved in high tech pursuits still believe in aphrodisiacs obtained from tiger/lion, paws, elephant tusks, and shark fins? (Posted on 26/01/2020 - 16 comments; 0 retweets; 11 likes)

There are some important keywords in Tweet #01 that evidence the relational duality between the hegemonic and normalised ‘modern world’ (i.e., the in-group) and the out-group. The latter is depicted as ‘these cultures’ who enjoy ‘strange things, foul foods and spread disgusting diseases’. Such characteristics mark (or stigmatise) the out-group as different or deviant from the normal pattern; however, the parameter utilised to measure the degree of abnormality is centred on the values and beliefs nurtured by the in-group.

Likewise, in Tweet #02, it is possible to notice a similar ideological construction which employs subtle elements of the ‘model minority’ stereotype. In this case, the user highlights what seems to be an irreconcilable cultural contradiction in that Chinese people are capable of producing state-

of-the-art technology while simultaneously accepting and nurturing a series of backward values and beliefs.

Deeply embedded in these tweets is the sentiment of strangeness regarding 'the other', which can also be found in the emblematic book authored by Rupert (1911) who describes 'strange' aspects associated with Asian people, such as their unintelligible language, the gods and entities they worship, and their eating habits. Thus, by highlighting the 'deviant' characteristics of the out-group, one reaffirms, reinforces, and legitimises the 'normal' attributes of the in-group. Moreover, since

VII. THE QUEST FOR A SCAPEGOAT

The global reach of the COVID-19 pandemic and the speed at which it has spread across all continents has helped create the appropriate conditions for people searching for someone to blame. Although the World Health Organization's guidelines regarding the naming of new infectious diseases clearly opposes the use of geographical regions or country names (WHO, 2015), COVID-19 soon became associated with China, as evidenced in the following Tweets.

Tweet #03: Chinese people are nasty, man. They have got the whole world f*** up. (Posted on 12/03/2020 - 2.8K comments; 19.7K retweets; 56.4K likes)

Tweet #04: The United States will be powerfully supporting those industries, like airlines and others, that are particularly affected by the Chinese Virus. We will be stronger than ever before. (Posted on 16/03/2020 - 124.7K comments; 150.8K retweets; 309.8K likes)

Tweet #05: Unbelievable. From TGR Leonardo (RAI 3), of 16/11/2015 report on a pulmonary super virus coronavirus created by the Chinese with bats and mice, very dangerous for humans (with related concerns). (Posted on 25/03/2020 - 4.5K comments; 3.3K retweets; 5.4 likes)

Tweet #06: A look inside the coronavirus lab where China prepared the stage for worldwide death. (Posted on 03/04/2020 - 3 comments; 1 retweet; 30 likes)

Tweet #07: Chinese are evil. They must take responsibility for COVID-19. (Posted on 15/04/2020 - 1 comment; 0 retweets; 9 likes)

the outbreak of COVID-19, there has been a multitude of messages on social media "linking [the infectious disease] to ostensibly exotic dietary practices and unsanitary behaviour of Chinese population, with representations depicting them as folk devils and dangerous, impure others" (Walsh 2020, p. 8). Thus, Tweet #01 and Tweet #02 not only coalesce with numerous other messages circulating in this platform, they also convey a series of ancient stigmatisation attributes that have resurfaced with renewed strength in the context of the pandemic and been amplified by social media platforms.

Tweet #08: Hope this scum Chinese is found and punished, but probably it will not happen because they are the f**** Chinese and they are just barbaric with their barbaric culture of killing and eating innocent animals and eating whatever f**** moves due to which we now have the Chinese virus. (Posted on 08/08/2020 - 0 comments; 0 retweets; 0 likes)

These tweets reveal important aspects regarding anti-Chinese sentiment. First, it becomes evident that COVID-19 has become a strong stigma marking the bodies of Chinese people. However, unlike ancient Greece or colonial Brazil, this mark is not as literal as before but nevertheless might leave a lasting and profound sore. In effect, pointing the fingers towards China, as seen in the sample of Tweets, does not occur by chance. The inner logic observed in these posts is that the 'strange', 'unusual', and 'backward' cultural habits of the Chinese might be the cause of the emergence of the virus and, consequently, the Chinese people should be held accountable for this. A similar pattern was found, for example, in a study conducted by Weiner and Perry (1988). The authors identified that, years ago, HIV positive patients were "held personally responsible and blamed for the onset of AIDS, which presumably were caused by a behavioural stigma" (Weiner and Perry, 1988, p. 745). Following this line of reasoning, the outbreak of both infectious diseases (HIV-AIDS and COVID-19) are constructed as the direct result of the 'unnatural' or 'uncivilized' habits of out-groups that have jeopardised and threatened modern Western civilization and its values, beliefs and 'normal' social behaviour.

The second relevant aspect that emerged from this sample of Tweets concerns the powerful influence of prominent figures in setting the trend regarding the narratives employed. Supporting evidence for this is found in Tweet #04 and Tweet

#05 posted, respectively, by Donald Trump (the US president at that time) and Matteo Salvini (an influential Italian far-right congressman). While posts by ordinary people usually trigger a low number of comments, retweets, and likes, as can be seen in the sample of Tweets in this study, the posts of these two public figures engaged thousands of users. One of the possible implications from this type of post is that numerous ordinary users might consider it legitimate to express converging ideologies regardless of any supporting evidence for their claims. In fact, as argued by Klein (2018), hateful discourse fostered on social media is often built on unfounded assumptions about the nature of 'the other'. Consequently, although it is not possible to assert that the sample of Tweets in the present

study are derived from those posted by prominent public figures, it is possible to notice convergent ideologies and stigmatising portrayals of Chinese people amongst them.

Another distinctive aspect emerging from the data is the underlying dynamic of inclusion vs exclusion between the in-group (i.e., Western society) and the out-group (i.e., Chinese), in that these Tweets objectively assign culpability to the latter. In effect, this scapegoating process is the result of a basic psychological mechanism in which, faced with an external threat beyond their control, people search for someone to blame and to whom they can attribute responsibility for that particular event (Schild *et al.*, 2020).

VIII. THE UNDESIRABLE CITIZEN

Among the wide variety of anti-Chinese discourses found on social media, one of the most common comprises strong manifestations conveying the embedded idea of sending Chinese people 'back home' or urging them to 'go away', as illustrated in the following set of Tweets:

Tweet #09: Infected Chinese. Go back home. (Posted on 11/02/2020 - 0 comments; 0 retweets; 0 likes)

Tweet #10: You virus infected Chinese. You have started a bio war against the West. Time to stop all Chinese coming to Australia, even permanent residents. You are worse than the plague. You piss off too. (Posted on 25/02/2020 - 0 comments; 0 retweets; 0 likes)

Tweet #11: You Chinese are the ones who brought it here. (Posted on 25/03/2020 - 0 comments; 0 retweets; 0 likes)

Tweet #12: You f*** Chinese scum. Seriously, I feel I will get banned from Twitter because I keep on saying shoot them. But I am serious. It makes me sick to the stomach. (Posted on 21/06/2020 - 5 comments; 0 retweets; 0 likes)

This sample of Tweets reveals certain stigmatisation attributes that are common in many discourses regarding Chinese people and were found not only in this set but also across the previous groups analysed. In Tweet #09, for example, the user expresses the generalised assumption that all Chinese people are infected and should therefore go away.

Moreover, although the user has said 'go back home', it can be inferred that this home is not here but rather there (i.e., in China). Likewise, Tweet #10 reinforces the association between Chinese people and infection. Moreover, in both Tweet #10 and Tweet #11, there is repetition of the scapegoating approach discussed in the previous section along with the manifestation of xenophobic ideas. Another aspect of note is the strong xenophobic idea embedded in Tweet #10 where the user expresses their concerns regarding the alleged 'threat' represented by China and even suggests suppressing residence rights to Chinese citizens living in Australia. Finally, Tweet #12 represents an example of the escalation of aggressive xenophobic discourses on social media. In fact, this type of behaviour coalesces with the argument raised by Coe *et al.* (2014, p. 662) that social media platforms tend to attract and "encourage disinhibited antisocial behaviour".

However, the relevant question concerns what it in fact means to urge people to leave a place or to say they are not welcome in a given social context. The embedded meaning in this discourse involves different intersectional elements. First, as addressed in the previous section, scapegoating tends to occur when people are confronted with challenges beyond their control. Second, although Asian people used to be labelled as a 'model minority', this does not mean average citizens easily accepted being less-favourably portrayed. This implies there may be some repressed anger that social media platforms have helped to unleash. Finally, they might also represent the re-emergence of old perceptions regarding 'strange people' as 'intruders', which is similar to the framing of migrants and refugees identified by Torkington and Ribeiro (2019).

Corroborating this argument, in the early 1900s Chinese immigrants in the US were considered not only an undesirable cohort but also as parasites whose presence could have detrimental impacts on the social fabric and threaten the values of the hegemonic in-group (Chandra, 2020). Ultimately, what can be interpreted from this sample of Tweets and is supported by the literature is that, from the

perspective of those tweeting these messages, Chinese people have represented not only the vector of a deadly threat to Western civilization (e.g., Tweet #06, Tweet #10, and Tweet #11), they are also illegitimate members of society and consequently should either be sent away or refused permission to enter and remain in Western countries.

IX. DISCUSSION

Among the varied aspects associated with the surge of anti-Chinese sentiment witnessed during the pandemic, there is an important and related reflection that is often absent in the literature. This is the question of whether this phenomenon is predominantly of a racist nature, xenophobic, or a combination of both? On the one hand, it is not hard to find news articles in the mainstream press that have addressed this phenomenon as racist manifestations (e.g. BBC, 2020b; Hemkentokrax, 2020; Songne, 2020). Likewise, in scholarly papers, different authors have adopted the same approach (Chandra, 2020; Kraus and Eun, 2020). These authors have characterised the phenomenon as racism due to the fact that the offensive discourses fostered both on social media and offline are targeted against Asian people in general, and Chinese people in particular. In other words, a racial group was targeted and stigmatised.

Conversely, there are also voices characterising this phenomenon as essentially xenophobic manifestations (Liu, 2020; Rafi, 2020; Schild *et al.*, 2020). These papers suggest that the authors of such material employ anti-Chinese sentiment and/or Sinophobia in their description of the phenomenon because xenophobic manifestations are mostly triggered by fear and panic regarding 'the other' (i.e., the alien with 'strange' and 'uncivilised' habits). Furthermore, while Sinophobia means a fear or dislike of Chinese people, xenophobia stands for dislike or aversion regarding foreigners. Thus, both terminologies address the fear (i.e., phobia) of the unknown and the 'difference' represented by the foreign citizen.

Nevertheless, the data gathered for the present study suggest that the phenomenon in fact exhibits overlapping characteristics of both racism and xenophobia. The most frequent terminologies employed by the users in the sample of Tweets are a) disgusting population, b) dirty population, c) backward population, d) barbaric population, e) go away, and f) eating [habits]. Some of these

expressions have been used to stigmatise and discriminate a racialised social groups and position them as inferior in comparison to the hegemonic Western in-group. Other terminologies have been used to express the idea of the social exclusion of Chinese and to position them as persona non grata or illegitimate members of society.

Consequently, rather than being fixed or absolute, the surge in anti-Chinese sentiment during the pandemic seems to have been circumstance-driven (i.e., dependent on the predominant ideology triggering aggressive discourses on social media) and as such displays intersecting characteristics of both racism and xenophobia.

X. CONCLUSION

COVID-19 still remains a very recent phenomenon, and it seems that in terms of health, there are more questions than definitive answers. The same applies to the pandemic's numerous societal impacts; therefore, further studies are needed to increase our understanding of the array of implications and changes this pandemic has brought to social relations. For this reason, one of the approaches adopted in the present study was to add a longitudinal perspective to the analysis. The aim was to demonstrate that the phenomenon of anti-Chinese sentiment dates back many decades and has resurfaced with the outbreak of COVID-19. Relevant literature (Rupert, 1911; Stoddard, 1921; Zhang, 2008) was drawn on to illustrate that, rather than disappearing over time, this sentiment has remained dormant in several Western societies. Complementing this historical perspective, the study also reviewed the concepts of stigma (Goffman, 1963; Weiner and Perry, 1988; Major and O'Brien, 2005) and the 'model minority' stereotype (Delener and Neelankavil, 1990; Cohen, 1992; Taylor and Stern, 1997; Kawai, 2005; Taylor *et al.*, 2005) which were of great relevance to this research.

What evolved from such considerations was that while ethnic minority groups in the US such as Hispanics and Afro Americans have experienced

enduring stigmatisation over the years, Asian Americans have instead experienced 'positive' stereotyping. Thus, being portrayed as possessing positive attributes such as being hardworking, intelligent, tech-savvy, business oriented, and so forth, might have brought two main benefits to the Asian community in the US and also elsewhere (Pon, 2000; Santos and Acevedo, 2013; Ho, 2014; Yeh, 2014). First, to a certain extent, it might have contributed to their social integration, given the fact that these positive attributes were not perceived by the in-group as a threat to their hegemonic status. Second, although there have been numerous criticisms regarding the negative impacts of the 'model minority' stereotype, it might have also shielded the Asian community from being as stigmatised as other ethnic minority groups in Western societies.

Nevertheless, the outbreak of COVID-19 has not only removed this 'protective' shield, it has also exposed the Chinese community to a myriad of stigmatisations whose ideas and depictions, embedded in numerous messages, coalesce with the ancient portrayal of Asian people commonly and openly fostered in the early twentieth century (Rupert, 1911; Stoddard, 1921; Armony and Velásquez, 2015; Chandra, 2020).

Another important component regarding the surge in anti-Chinese sentiment during the pandemic is the fact that most of these messages have been disseminated on social media platforms. While in the early twentieth century printed newspapers were the main channel through which to convey anti-Chinese sentiment, this central role has now been assumed by modern digital technology. One of its main characteristics is the fact that social media enables users to construct and instantly disseminate a wide variety of aggressive anti-Chinese discourses, which can reach and engage a wide audience of like-minded people and exponentially amplify their voices not only in the specific social context in which they were generated but also globally. A critical discourse analysis of the sample of Tweets gathered for the present study revealed that such discourses on social media have framed Chinese people according to three main categories: a) strange people, b) the perfect scapegoat, and c) the undesirable citizen.

Based on this qualitative analysis, it was argued that although some voices classify contemporary anti-Chinese sentiment as racism and others as xenophobic manifestations, the discourses circulating on social media targeted at the Chinese people exhibit characteristics of both. This suggests that the specificity of the outbreak of COVID-19

(i.e., starting in a well-defined location rather than simultaneously in different countries) has contributed to the development of this overlap. It is also important to explain that this interpretation does not imply that Chinese people might be exposed to greater discrimination and social marginalisation than other ethnic minority groups. What is being argued is that the discourses analysed indicate that contemporary anti-Chinese sentiment is permeated with both racist and xenophobic sentiments.

Consequently, the strong networking capabilities afforded by social media platforms not only allow the wide and instantaneous dissemination of the discourses identified in the paper, they also (in)directly contribute towards establishing an atmosphere of collective panic and divisionism in society (Trindade, 2019; Walsh, 2020). Ultimately, the aim of the people fostering these racist and xenophobic discourses on social media is to remove the 'model minority' shield of Asian people and replace it with the stigma of COVID-19, transforming them into 'outsiders' within that social setting.

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